

INFLUENCE OF ENDPST MATERIALS ON SUB-SURFACE RAILHEAD MATERIAL DAMAGE OF INSULATED RAIL JOINTS DUE TO WHEEL/RAIL CONTACT LOADINGS

Nirmal Kumar Mandal

Centre for Railway Engineering, Central Queensland University, Queensland 4702, Australia

Keywords: Rail joints, Composite material endpost, FEA, Sub-surface damage, Cyclic ratchetting, Elastoplastic material behaviour

ABSTRACT

Insulated rail joints (IRJs) are very important for signalling systems in controlling trains on a railway track. They are also helpful to locate broken rails. The IRJs are considered as one of the weakest links of a railway track. The bending rigidity of an IRJ is only 2/3rd that of continuous rail. Consequently, larger stresses and deflections are experienced in the vicinity of IRJs. It is, therefore, necessary to give proper attention in designing the geometrical configuration of IRJs, focussing on composite endpost materials and other parameters to reduce plastic flow and stress states.

This paper addresses the question of which stress state causes plastic deformation of IRJs? To answer that question, a 3D finite element analysis (FEA) is carried out using the Abaqus code to focus on damage and plastic deformation of sub-surface railhead material considering different composite endpost materials. At the wheel/rail contact patch on IRJs, vertical wheel impacts up to a total of 2000 cycles in the form of non-Hertzian pressure loadings are applied. A non-linear isotropic kinematic material hardening rule is applied. The subsequent analysis considers the sub-surface railhead damage to rank the commonly used endpost materials (fibre glass (fb), nylon 66 (ny) and polytetrafluoroethylene (ptfe)) based on the mechanical behaviour of the IRJs. The mechanical behaviour of ny and ptfe are benchmarked against that of fb for 50, 1000 and 2000 loading cycles. Significant sub-surface material damage occurs down to a depth of 8mm from the top of the railhead and, below 12mm depth, the material behaviour is elastic. Almost all damage parameters exhibit a similar damage level (flat type) for a depth up to 8mm initially and, as the cyclic loading increases, the flat pattern damage changes to a horizontal 'Bell-Shape' pattern indicating that the fb is a better endpost material to control sub-surface railhead material damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Conventional mechanical bolted joints are used for connecting strings of continuous welded rail (CWR), for temporary repairs, and in sharp curves where rapid wear forces regular rail replacements. However, IRJs are most important for electrical signalling systems to locate trains and broken rails. There is a tendency of reducing the number of IRJs in CWR track, but it is deemed impossible to replace them fully. Therefore, proper attention should be given to design the components of IRJs including endpost materials as they are one of the weakest links of the track structure.

Polymers, composite materials, thermosetting plastics and thermoplastics have wide industrial applications in ventilation, marine, and coal mining sectors. The popular polymers and composite materials are: fibreglass (fb), nylon (ny), polytetrafluoroethylene (ptfe), polycarbonate (pc), polystyrene (ps), polypropylene (pp), aramid (kevlar 49), carbon fibre-epoxy, polyvinylchloride (pvc), melamine formaldehyde, urea formaldehyde etc. Composite and polymer materials are also useful in railway track. In IRJs, fb is the most commonly used endpost material. Other popular endpost materials are ny and ptfe.

There are a few early literature papers available presenting performance focussing on mechanical rail joints [1, 2] and more recently focusing also on IRJs [3, 4]. The effects of endpost materials on mechanical behaviour and railhead and sub-surface material damage due to cyclic wheel loading is not yet available fully. There is some literature which is generally focussed on residual stresses and strain and plastic deformation information in the top surface the head of a rail end. Recently, Mandal [5, 6]

studied the effects of three endpost materials (fb, ny and ptfe) on railhead damage relating to plastic deformation of railhead top material in the vicinity of the IRJs. A detailed rail sub-surface damage pattern is deemed important for product design and development purposes

This study addresses a few key points of mechanical behaviour of IRJs due to the soft endpost materials used. They are:

- Wheel load sharing by endpost material is less compared to rail and the degree of the load sharing is based on the Young's Modulus values of endpost materials. Thereby different stress levels can result in railhead material. Therefore, there can potentially be a hypothesis linking endpost material properties and the degree of railhead damage.
- Ranking of endpost material influence on railhead stress levels at different loading cycles is necessary.
- Performance of various endpost materials relating to the railhead sub-surface stress levels for the same loading cycles should be available in the literature for product design and analysis.
- Detailed information on the location of sub-surface plastic zones of railhead material is necessary. Is this information dependent of loading cycles?
- Which stress component is responsible for damaging the top railhead and sub-surface material?

It is necessary to carry out a detailed study of sub-surface damage of railhead material of some popular endpost materials (fb, ny and ptfe), benchmarking the mechanical behaviour of ny and ptfe against the most commonly used fb. This research is focusing on enhancing a hypothesis of the effect of endpost material on railhead material degradation, namely that endpost materials with higher Young's Modulus and lower Poisson's ratio perform better.

2 METHODS

A 3D finite element analysis (FEA) is conducted to model IRJs through a global model and a sub-model for local damage analysis. A cyclic vertical wheel load is applied on the railhead top surface in the vicinity of an IRJ in pressure form considering a non-Hertzian pressure distribution. Section 2.1 discusses a global FEA rail joint modelling of a 5mm endpost thickness IRJ, Section 2.2 discusses a sub-model of part of the railhead in the vicinity of the IRJ. A non-linear isotropic/kinematic hardening material behaviour was considered for the contact zone of the wheel/rail interface. A detailed description of sub-modelling of the IRJ and of elasto-plastic material behaviour was presented in Mandal and Dhanasekar [7].

2.1 A rail joint global model

Figure 1(a) shows part of the FEA model of the IRJ. Total length of the IRJ model considered for this study is 12m. This length is deemed sufficient when considering boundary conditions of a finite rail piece [8]. A 2.4m length is a solid rail model taken from the 12m rail with a 1/20 rail cant position as per Australian Standard 1085.12 [9]. Two beam models (not shown), each 4.8m long, are connected to the ends of the solid model by equation constraints in ABAQUS to ensure zero displacement and rotation of beams and rail relative to one another. This ensures all six DOFs are transferred from the solid rail model to the beam models. Other parameters are: 5mm endpost thickness, 6 bolt joint plates, IRJ is centrally suspended between two adjacent sleepers (Figure 1(a)), 0.7m centre to centre sleeper spacing. Figure 1(b) shows the 174kN wheel loading in pressure form on the IRJ. ABAQUS's part and section modules are used to construct the IRJ model and apply homogeneous section and elastic-plastic material properties respectively. The top critical area of the head of the rail (dark part of Figure 1(a)) is defined with high mesh density to account for elastic-plastic material deformation. The high mesh density part is drawn separately and connected to the remaining part of the IRJ model by tie constraints. The other part of the IRJ model is elastic. Table 1 presents the Young's Modulus and Poisson's ratio of rail steel and endpost materials, and Table 2 the elastic-plastic material properties of the top surface of the head-hardened rail.

Figure 1: (a) FEA global model of IRJ and (b) FEA sub-model showing loading on IRJ and location of sub-model

Name	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio
Head hardened rail steel	207000	0.3
Fibre-glass (fb)	45000	0.19
Nylon 66 (ny)	1590	0.39
PTFE (ptfe)	400	0.46

Table 1: Rail steel and endpost material properties [10]

σ_y (MPa)	K_∞ (MPa)	b'	c (MPa)	γ
780	152	3.97	393000	8.3

Table 2: Elastic-plastic properties of rail top surface material (the high mesh density part shown in Figure 6(a)) [10]

2.2 A rail joint sub-model

The sub-modelling is a local FEA modelling strategy for a more accurate simulation study. A critical section of the top surface of the railhead in the vicinity of the free rail ends of the IRJ (Figure 1 (b)) is employed for a sub-modelling study, keeping the same magnitude of x, y, z coordinates. Figure 1 (b) also shows the location of the sub-model part in the global rail joint model. Four sub-model meshes (Figure 2) were considered in this study for an initial mesh convergence study to select an optimum mesh (mesh 3). The nodes and element numbers of the different meshes are shown in Table

3. Figure 3 indicates the coordinate system directions where 3 indicates the longitudinal direction, 2 the vertical direction and 1 the lateral direction and the figure includes the dimensions of the sub-model. A detailed description of this sub-modelling technique was presented previously [7]. PE33 represents the longitudinal plastic strain component, PE22 the vertical plastic strain component and so on.

Figure 2: Four sub-model meshes

Figure 3: Selected sub-model of railhead top surface with dimensions

Meshes	Nodes	Elements
Mesh 1	13,338	11,492
Mesh 2	29,376	26,180
Mesh 3	46,166	41,600
Mesh 4	90,240	83,444

Table 3: Node and element numbers of four sub-model meshes

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Output database (odb) files obtained from FEA global and sub-models are considered here to rank railhead sub-surface plastic deformation due to the three endpost materials used: fb, ny and ptf. Two damage parameters, namely vertical plastic strains (PE22) and residual von-Mises stresses (von) are considered for 50, 1000 and 2000 vertical wheel load cycles. A contour plot of contact pressure (Figure 4) on the IRJ is initially presented to show the simulation accuracy of the study. It was indicated above that a vertical wheel load of 174kN was applied cyclically in a pressure form over the IRJ with a peak pressure of 2500MPa. The maximum pressure of 2412MPa is observed (Figure 4) for fb endpost material with an error level of 3.52% which is deemed acceptable. Therefore, other simulation data from odb files for PE22 and von are presented herewith.

Figure 4: A contour plot of contact pressure on IRJ for fb endpost material at the end of 2000 loading cycles

Figures 5 to 7 show the variation of residual vertical plastic strain (PE 22) in the railhead sub-surface for fb, ny and ptfe after 50, 1000 and 2000 loading cycles. It is evident in Figure 5 for 50 loading cycles that, for a shallow depth up to 1mm, the PE 22 is increasing regularly for all endpost materials. However, from 1 mm to 7 mm, there is not much change in vertical plastic strain, showing an almost constant value in the sub-surface zone for all endpost materials. In this study, this is described as a ‘flat type’ damage pattern. For a greater depth, the plastic deformation (damage) is reduced linearly from 7 mm to zero at around 11 mm to 12 mm sub-surface depth of railhead material. All endpost materials exhibit similar damage patterns in the sub-surface of the railhead after 50 loading cycles. However, for 1000 and 2000 loading cycles, the shallow sub-surface damage pattern is different to that of 50 loading cycles. The flat pattern damage in the sub-surface no longer exists. A sharp change occurs in plastic deformation in the sub-surface depth. The flat pattern damage changes to a horizontal ‘Bell-Shape’ pattern. The peak value of the damage parameter is concentrated at 2 mm to 3 mm sub-surface depth, and the plots indicate that the fb is a better endpost material to control sub-surface railhead material damage, followed by ptfe and ny respectively. At 2000 loading cycles the railhead damage is more compared to that of 1000 cycles in all endpost cases while keeping the same horizontal Bell-Shaped pattern. This damage pattern is evident for a single endpost material (fb) for all three loading cycles (Figure 8). It shows how a flat type damage pattern changes to the Bell-Shaped pattern. This latter pattern in the area of railhead damage is newly identified by this study.

Figure 5: Residual PE 22 for fb, ny and ptfe at 50 loading cycles

Figure 6: Residual PE 22 for fb, ny and ptfе at 1000 loading cycles

Figure 7: Residual PE 22 for fb, ny and ptfе at 2000 loading cycles

Figure 8: Residual PE 22 for fb at 50, 1000 and 2000 loading cycles

On the other hand, Figures 9 to 11 present another damage parameter, called the residual von-Mises stress component, for three endpost materials with Figure 9 for 50 loading cycles, Figure 10 for 1000 loading cycles and Figure 11 for 2000 loading cycles. For 50 loading cycles, the flat type damage pattern exists from the top railhead surface to nearly 8 mm sub-surface depth of railhead. Then, for all three endpost materials, the residual von-Mises component linearly reduces to zero at 12 mm to 13

mm depth. At greater depth after this range, the material behavior is fully elastic. Two important patterns of initially flat and then linear for the von-Mises damage parameter is evident in Figure 9 as compared to the three patterns in Figure 5 of initially linear, then flat and finally linear again.

The flat pattern of damage in Figure 9 at the shallow sub-surface depth changes as the number of loading cycles increase. For 1000 and 2000 loading cycles, a complex form of damage pattern exists: the new Bell-Shaped pattern. For both 1000 and 2000 loading cycle, less damage is seen for fb endpost material, followed by ptfe and ny. As the number of cycles is increasing, more damage is occurring. This trend can be seen clearly in Figure 12 with an obvious change of damage pattern from 50 cycles to higher cycles for ptfe. A decay of damage rate is also evident, suggesting more damage occurred initially (from 50 cycles to 1000 cycles) and then reduced (from 1000 cycles to 2000 cycles). The decay of the ratchetting rate found in this study supports previous studies [11, 12]. However, the change of the Flat damage pattern to a horizontal Bell-Shaped pattern is quite new. Considering these data, the endpost materials are ranked as fb, prfe and ny focusing on less sub-surface railhead material damage.

All data stated above suggests that fb endpost material, whose Young’s Modulus is highest and Poisson’s ratio is lowest among the three endpost materials considered, is better for controlling railhead sub-surface damage. The opposite is not true for the lowest performing endpost material (ny). Therefore, it is hard to propose a hypothesis directly relating sub-surface railhead material damage to elastic material properties (Young’s Modulus and Poisson’s ratio) considering three endpost materials only.

Figure 9: Residual von-Mises stresses for fb, ny and ptfe at 50 loading cycles

Figure 10: Residual von-Mises stresses for fb, ny and ptfe at 1000 loading cycles

Figure 11: Residual von-Mises stresses for fb, ny and ptfe at 2000 loading cycles

Figure 12: Residual von-Mises stresses for ptfe at 50, 1000 and 2000 loading cycles

9 CONCLUSIONS

A detailed stress analysis was carried out on a standard 6 bolt IRJ of standard Australian design considering different endpost materials by applying a wheel loading that yields a contact stress over the yield strength of the rail steel. A wheel load of 174kN with a peak pressure load of 2500MPa was considered without any longitudinal creep force at the contact zone. The ratchetting material behaviour of railhead material can be expected. The following conclusions can be made based on the observation of this study:

- At a shallow sub-surface depth, a Flat type damage pattern is observed for 50 loading cycles.
- As the loading cycles increase, the Flat damage pattern changes to a horizontal Bell-Shaped pattern with less damage for fb endpost material.
- As the loading cycles increase, a decay in ratchetting rate is observed.
- Among the three endpost materials considered, fb is the best material relating to less sub-surface railhead material damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks go to Prof. M. Dhanasekar for his meticulous guidance to finish this research. Tim McSweeney, Adjunct Research Fellow, CRE is thankfully acknowledged for his advice at many stages of this ongoing study.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Wise, D. Lindsay, I. G. T. Duncan (1960). The strength of rails with particular reference to rail joints. Proc. of Institution of Mechanical Engineers, 174 (9): 371-407.
- [2] H. H. Jenkins, J. E. Stephenson, G. A. Clayton, G. W. Morland, D. Lyon (1974). The effect of track and vehicle parameters on wheel/rail vertical dynamic force. Railway Engineering Journal, 3: 2-16.
- [3] Z. Yang, A. Boogaard, Z. Wei, J. Liu, R. Dollevoet, Z. Li (2018). Numerical study of wheel-rail impact contact solutions at an insulated rail joint. International Journal of Mechanical Sciences, 138-139: 310-322.

- [4] M. Gallou, M. Forest, E. Al-Hamalawi, C. Hardwick (2018). Assessing the deflection behaviour of mechanical and insulated rail joints using finite element analysis. *Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*, 232 (9): 2290-2308.
- [5] N. K. Mandal (2016). FEA to assess plastic deformation of railhead material damage of insulated rail joints with fibreglass and nylon endposts. *Wear*, 366-367: 3-12.
- [6] N. K. Mandal (2016). Finite element analysis of the mechanical behaviour of insulated rail joints due to impact loadings. *Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*, 230(3): 759-773.
- [7] N. K. Mandal, and M. Dhanasekar (2013). Sub-modelling for the ratchetting failure of insulated rail joints. *International Journal of Mechanical Science*, 75: 110-122.
- [8] J. Igwemezie, and A. T. Nguyen, Anatomy of joint bar failures, *Railway Track and Structures*, July 2009; 31-37.
- [9] AS 1085.12: Railway track material: Insulated joint assemblies, Standards Australia, 2002.
- [10] N. K. Mandal (2017). Ratchetting damage of railhead material of gapped rail joints with reference to free rail end effects. *Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*, 231(2): 211-225.
- [11] N. K. Mandal (2014). Ratchetting of railhead material of insulated rail joints (IRJs) with reference to endpost thickness. *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 45: 347-362.
- [12] N. K. Mandal (2015). Plastic ratchetting of railhead material in the vicinity of insulated rail joints with wheel and thermal loads. *Wear*, 330-331: 540-553.